

cultural practices to favor high GM buildup, including close spacing (15 × 15 cm), continuous standing water of 2-5 cm, and frequent N application. Susceptible checks Jaya in Cuttack and TN1 in Sakoli were interspersed in the plots at the beginning, end, and after every 10 test entries to serve as indicators for GM buildup. Only plants completely free from infestation were rated resistant (R), while those showing any infestation rated susceptible (S).

TN1 had 100% GM-infested hills and 75-89% infested tillers (silvershoots). Jaya had 99-100% infested hills and 59-73% infested tillers.

Brown planthopper (BPH)-resistant varieties developed at Moncompu, Kerala

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The BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) has caused extensive damage to Asian rice crops. Although the pest was reported in Kerala during 1958 and 1962, the first severe outbreak occurred in 1973-74, damaging about 50,000 ha of rice. Grain yield loss was 10-70% and at times reached 100%.

Host plant resistance is the logical approach to BPH control.

Breeding programs for BPH-resistant varieties began in 1973 at RRS. BPH-

Damage ratings were consistent in both years at both centers. Entries S in Sakoli but R in Cuttack were ARC5158, ARC6221, RPW6-4 (S.S), Leaug 152, Shakti, Samalei, OB677, Orumundakan, CR294-548, CR3 17-166, CR319-644, CR315-621, CR318-548-7, CR410-3225, CR410-3225-2, CR308-408, CR309-268, ARC5984, Swimphul, CR394-6056, CR410-6018, and CR392-5085-2.

Entries R in both Sakoli and Cuttack were AC1224, MNP76, PTB10, Banglei, CR57-MR 1523, CR311-134, CR157-212, Aganni, Eswarakorra, Velluthacheera, NHTA 8, and T1477.

resistant donors such as PTB20, Kochuvithu, Karivennel, IR1539, PTB33, ARC6650, and IR1561, and modern varieties such as IR8, IR11, Triveni, and Jaya were used.

Promising selections were obtained from crosses IR8/PTB20, IR11/Kochuvithu, IR8/Karivennel, Trivenil IR1539, Jaya/PTB33, ARC6650/Jaya, and IR1561/PTB33. Eight varieties were released from them during 1978-90.

We studied the reaction of seedlings to the local BPH biotype using the bulk seedling test. Varieties were also screened in the field under heavy natural incidence. Resistance was scored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*. Results are presented in the table. □

Plant characters and BPH score of selections bred for BPH resistance in Kerala, India.

Variety	Parentage	Plant height (cm)	Crop duration (d)	Panicles (no./hill)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Grain type ^a	Protein content (%)	Reaction to BPH ^b		Release (year)
								Lab	Field	
MO 4 (Bhadra)	IR8m/PTB20	81	120 ^c 135 ^d	20.0	5.5	SB	10.2	2.8	2.5	1978
MO 5 (Asha)	IR11/Kochuvithu	85	120	7.5	6.0	LB	9.4	2.6	2.5	1980
MO 6 (Pavizham)	IR8/Karivennel	90	120	7.5	6.0	SB	7.5	2.0	2.3	1982
MO 7 (Karthika)	Triveni/IR1539	90	110	7.5	6.5	LB	10.6	2.0	2.0	1985
MO 8 (Aruna)	Jaya/PTB33	90	110	12.0	6.5	MB	9.6	2.2	1.7	1990
MO 9 (Makam)	ARC6650/Jaya	85	110	12.0	6.5	SB	9.4	1.7	2.5	1990
MO 10 (Remya)	Jaya/PTB33	110	120	10.0	6.5	LB	10.9	2.3	2.6	1990
MO 11 (Kanakam)	IR1561/PTB33	110	125	8.0	7.0	MB	9.5	1.6	2.0	1990
TN1 (susceptible check)		75	105	12.0	—	MB	—	9.0	9.0	—
PTB33 (resistant check)		135	130	6.0	—	MB	—	2.7	2.3	—

^a Cooking quality of all selections was good. SB = short bold, LB = long bold, MB = medium bold. All test varieties have red kernels.

^b By the *Standard evaluation system for rice*. ^c Dry season. ^d Wet season.

Orumundakan and its derivatives CR308-408 and CR309-268 were R in NCAP but S in Sakoli, Eswarakorra was R in Sakoli but S in NCAP, and Velluthacheera was S in NCAP but R at Sakoli. Sakoli GM was also different from that in Ranchi (III). CR57-MR 1523 was R in Sakoli and S in Ranchi; Kakatiya was the opposite.

Eswarakorra was R at both locations. PTB10 and its derivatives R296-120 and CR157-212 were R at all locations. Sakoli GM populations should be treated as a distinct biotype based on these results. □

Pest resistance—other pests

Upland rice cultivars resistant to parasitic weed *Striga hermonthica*

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Striga spp. are parasitic weeds of maize, sorghum, millet, and upland rice in Africa. No single method exists for controlling striga effectively. The pink-colored *S. hermonthica* (Del.) Benth. has become a serious problem in upland rice in western Kenya. We studied whether rice cultivars differed in relative resistance to *S. hermonthica*.

Forty upland rice lines from various sources were evaluated for reaction to striga during the 1990 short-rains cropping season (Sep-Dec). We conducted the experiment in a farmer's field that had a history of striga incident at Mbita Point under rainfed upland conditions (900 mm rain/yr). The soil is a calcaro-vertic Fluvisol with pH 8.1 and 0.9% organic C; each 100-g sample has CEC 37.5 meq, 0.1 meq K, and 36 meq P. Rice was planted in rows, 30 cm apart in 3- × 5-m plots, with four replications.

Striga plants were uprooted from plots at 95 d after rice emergence, dried, and weighed. Rice entries IR38547-B-B-7-2-2, IR47255-B-B-5-4, IR47697-4-3-1, and IR49255-B-B-5-2 were striga-free